

Enantioselective synthesis of both enantiomers of bgugaine employing the SAMP-hydrazone method[†]

Dieter Enders* and Christoph Thiebes

Institut für Organische Chemie, RWTH Aachen, Professor-Pirlet-Strasse 1, D-52074 Aachen, Germany

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The synthesis of both enantiomers of bgugaine by 1,2-addition of organometallic reagents to aldehyde-SAMP-hydrazone, followed by N-N-bond cleavage and cyclization is described. The new method provides an entry into the preparation of enantiomerically pure 2-substituted pyrrolidines.

(*R*)-(-)-Bgugaine [(*R*)-(-)-7], a pyrrolidine alkaloid extracted from the tubers of *Arisarum vulgare*, shows antibacterial and antimycotic activities^{1,2}. The determination of the absolute configuration was achieved by asymmetric synthesis utilizing Meyer's protocol², whilst a second asymmetric synthesis was based on a Sharpless asymmetric dihydroxylation approach³.

We now wish to report a new asymmetric synthesis of both enantiomers of bgugaine employing the highly diastereoselective nucleophilic 1,2-addition to aldehyde-SAMP-hydrazone. This approach has already been successfully used in the asymmetric synthesis of both enantiomers of the piperidine alkaloid coniine⁴. The synthesis began with a Swern oxidation of the monoprotected diol **1**, which was prepared according to a literature procedure⁵, followed by condensation of the resulting crude aldehyde with the chiral hydrazine (*S*)-1-amino-2-(methoxymethyl)pyrrolidine (SAMP). Hydrazone (*S*)-**2** was obtained in 96% yield over two steps. Although our experience during the synthesis of coniine showed that organoytterbium reagents performed better than the corresponding lithium reagents in terms of diastereoselectivity and yield in the addition to aldehyde SAMP hydrazones, we tested both reagents. Tetradecyllithium was prepared by halogen-metal exchange from 1-iodotetradecane with two equivalents of *tert*-butyllithium. Treatment of (*S*)-**2** with three equivalents of tetradecyllithium at -85° in THF furnished hydrazine (*R,S*)-**3** in 85% yield. The reaction proceeded with complete asymmetric induction and only one diastereomer could be detected by ¹³C NMR (*de* ≥ 96%). The organoytterbium reagent was obtained by treatment of three equivalents of tetradecyllithium with one equivalent of ytterbium trichloride. The reaction of this reagent with (*S*)-**2** gave (*R,S*)-**3** as a single diastereomer in a lower yield of 78%. The N-N-bond of hydrazine (*R,S*)-**3** was cleaved by reaction with borane-tetrahydrofuran complex in THF followed by methanolysis. The resulting crude amine was

treated with methyl chloroformate to give carbamate (*R*)-**4** in 72% yield. (*S*)-2-(Methoxymethyl)pyrrolidine (SMP) which is generated as a byproduct in the cleavage reaction can be recovered and transformed to SAMP. After successful synthesis of the enantiomerically highly enriched carbamate (*R*)-**4** it was possible to synthesize (*R*)-(-)-bgugaine using standard procedures as shown in Scheme 1. Removal of the silyl-protecting group and mesylation followed by cyclization upon treatment with potassium *tert*-butoxide provided N-protected pyrrolidine (*R*)-**6** in excellent yield (88% over three steps). Reduction of (*R*)-**6** with lithium aluminum hydride gave (*R*)-(-)-bgugaine [(*R*)-(-)-**7**] in 84% yield and high enantiomeric purity (*ee* ≥ 96%, determined by polarimetry).

Scheme 1. Reagents : (a) (COCl)₂, DMSO, Et₃N, -78° → room temp., (b) SAMP, 0° → room temp., (c) 3 *n*-C₁₄H₂₉Li + YbCl₃, THF, -85° → room temp., (c') 3 *n*-C₁₄H₂₉Li, THF, -85° → room temp., (d) borane-THF, THF, reflux; then MeOH, room temp., (e) ClCO₂Me, Et₂O, 0° → room temp., (f) TBAF, THF, room temp., (g) MsCl, Et₃N, CH₂Cl₂, 0°; h) KO^tBu, THF, 0° → room temp., (i) LiAlH₄, THF, reflux.

[†] Dedicated to Professor. D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

In order to synthesize (*S*)-(+)-bgugaine [(*S*)-(+)-7], we repeated the sequence described above according to the concept of 'synthon control of enantioselectivity'⁶. The side-chain of the hydrazone was therefore exchanged by that of the nucleophile, correspondingly an organocerium reagent prepared from 3-*tert*-butyldimethylsiloxypropyllithium and cerium trichloride was added to the C–N double bond of pentadecanal SAMP hydrazone (*S*)-8 (Scheme 2). In this case, the organocerium reagent performed best in terms of yield and diastereoselectivity. This resulted in the formation of hydrazine (*S,S*)-3 in 72% yield, which was converted to carbamate (*S*)-4 in the way described for (*R*)-4. In this case, we found that organocerium reagents performed as well as the organoytterbium reagent in terms of diastereoselectivity but showed better yields. The diastereomeric excess was again determined by ¹³C NMR to be 92%. Having carbamate (*S*)-4 in hands, we were able to repeat the sequence described above to synthesize the unnatural enantiomer of bgugaine in a total yield of 37% and high enantiomeric purity (ee = 92%, determined by polarimetry) starting from (*S*)-8.

Scheme 2. Reagents : (a) $\text{LiCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OTBS} + \text{CeCl}_3$, THF, $-85^\circ \rightarrow$ room temp., (b) borane-THF, THF, reflux; then MeOH, room temp., (c) ClCO_2Me , Et_2O , $0^\circ \rightarrow$ room temp.

In conclusion, both enantiomers of bgugaine have been prepared in good yield and high enantiomeric purity starting from aldehyde-SAMP-hydrazone. This new practical approach to the preparation of optically pure 2-substituted pyrrolidines, offers great flexibility and should be useful for the synthesis of other pyrrolidine and indolizidine alkaloids.

Experimental

(*2S*)-1-[4-*tert*-Butyldimethylsiloxy]butylidene]-2-(methoxymethyl)-1-pyrrolidinamine [(*S*)-2] : To a solution of oxalyl chloride (2.72 ml, 30 mmol) in dichloromethane (15 ml) at -78° was slowly added a solution of dimethylsulfoxide (2.94 ml, 40 mmol) in dichloromethane (32 ml). After stirring for 15 min at -78° a solution of 4-(*tert*-butyldimethyl-

siloxy-1-butanol (1) (4.08 g, 20 mmol) in dichloromethane (60 ml) was added slowly and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min, followed by addition of triethylamine (8 ml). The solution was slowly warmed to room temperature and water (20 ml) was added. The organic phase was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted three times with a total of 300 ml of dichloromethane and the combined organic layers was washed with an aqueous solution of potassium hydrogen sulfate (20%), saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate solution and brine. After drying over magnesium sulfate and evaporation of the solvent, the crude aldehyde was obtained as a yellow liquid to which SAMP (2.60 g, 20 mmol) was added slowly at 0° . The reaction mixture was stirred for additional 60 min at room temperature and ether (150 ml) was added. After drying over magnesium sulfate and evaporation of the solvent, the resulting residue was purified by flash column chromatography on silica (petroleum ether/ethyl acetate, 6 : 1), yielding [(*S*)-2] (5.89 g, 89%) as a colorless oil (Found : C, 60.79; H, 11.13; N, 9.10. Calcd. : C, 61.10; H, 10.89; N, 8.91%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -82.5$ (c 1.35, CHCl_3); ν_{max} (neat) 2953 (s), 2929 (s), 2887 (s), 2857 (s), 1606 (w), 1472 (s), 1447 (m), 1387 (m), 1361 (m), 1340 (m), 1301 (w), 836 (s), 814 (m), 776 (s), 663 (w) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.05 (6H, s), 0.89 (9H, s), 1.65–2.01 (6H, m), 2.28 (2H, td, J 7.0/5.4 Hz, 2.72 (1H, m), 3.37 (3H, s), 3.33–3.45 (3H, m), 3.57 (1H, m), 3.65 (2H, m), 6.66 (1H, t, J 5.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -5.26, 18.38, 22.16, 26.00, 26.64, 29.61, 30.91, 50.43, 59.21, 62.70, 63.52, 74.92, 138.65; MS (70 eV) m/z (%) 314 (8; M^+), 269 (100; $\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3$), 200 (10; $\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{NCH}_2\text{OCH}_3$), 115 (8; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9(\text{H}_3\text{C})_2\text{Si}^+$), 106 (9), 101 (8), 89 (12), 75 (13), 73 (59; 115), 70 (24; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}^+$), 59 (10).

N-[(*1R*)-1-(3-{*tert*-Butyldimethylsiloxy}propyl)pentadecyl]-2-(*2S*)-2-(methoxymethyl)pyrrolidinamine [(*R,S*)-3] : To a solution of 1-iodotetradecane (9.72 g, 30 mmol) in dry ether (30 ml) at -18° was slowly added *tert*-butyllithium in *n*-hexane (33.8 ml, 1.6 M, 54 mmol). After 30 min of stirring at this temperature, the solution was slowly warmed to room temperature and stirred for 90 min. The pale yellow solution was then cooled to -85° whereupon a solution of (*S*)-2 (3.77 g, 12 mmol) in dry THF (12 ml) was added over a period of 45 min. The resulting slurry was stirred for another 60 min at this temperature and allowed to warm up to room temperature over a period of 15 h. The reaction mixture was treated with saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (30 ml) and after separation of the organic layer the aqueous phase was extracted three times with a total of 450 ml of ether. The combined organic layers was dried over magnesium sulfate and evaporated under reduced pres-

sure. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography on silica (petroleum ether/diethyl ether, 2 : 1) gave (*R,S*)-**3** (5.21 g, 85%) as a colorless oil, HREIMS calcd. *m/z* 512.473708, found *m/z* 512.473613; $[\alpha]_D^{27} = -31.5$ (*c* 1.00, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) 2960 (s), 2920 (s), 2860 (s), 1530 (s), 1450 (s), 1230 (s), 1100 (s), 830 (m), 780 (m) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.05 (6H, s), 0.89 (12H, m), 1.21–1.77 (34H, m), 1.88 (1H, m), 2.15 (2H, m), 2.56 (1H, m), 2.71 (1H, m), 3.35 (3H, s), 3.39 (1H, m), 3.53 (1H, dd, *J* 9.1/3.9 Hz), 3.60 (2H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -5.25, 14.10, 18.34, 20.94, 22.68, 25.25, 25.95 (2C), 26.18, 28.81, 29.15, 29.34, 29.64 (5C), 30.13, 31.90, 33.28, 57.66, 58.31, 58.96, 63.31, 65.94, 75.05; MS (70 eV) *m/z* (%) 512 (22, M⁺), 468 (100, M⁺-CH₂COCH₃), 340 (17), 129 (27).

Methyl N-[(1R)-1-(3-{tert-butyl dimethylsiloxy}propyl)pentadecyl]carbamate [(R)-4] : To a solution of (*R,S*)-**3** (4.0 g, 7.8 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) was added a solution of borane-tetrahydrofuran complex in THF (78 ml, 1 M, 78 mmol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed under argon for 5 h. After cooling to room temperature, dry methanol (24 ml) was added dropwise and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. A solution of hydrogen peroxide (8 ml; 30%) in methanol (16 ml) was added to the residue. After stirring for 15 h at room temperature, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the remainder was extracted three times with a total of 300 ml of ether. The combined organic layers was washed with saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate solution and brine, dried over magnesium sulfate and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in ether (100 ml) and triethylamine (3.53 g, 35 mmol) was added. At 0° methyl chloroformate (3.31 g, 35 mmol) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for additional 60 min. The white precipitate was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography on silica (petroleum ether/ethyl acetate, 6 : 1) yielded (*R*)-**4** (2.59 g, 73%) as white waxy solid (Found : C, 67.75; H, 12.05; N, 2.84. Calcd. : C, 68.21; H, 12.11; N, 3.06%); $[\alpha]_D^{24} = -1.0$ (*c* 1.02, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3319 (s), 2917 (s), 2850 (s), 1693 (s), 1544 (s), 1469 (m), 1353 (m), 1297 (m), 1258 (m), 1040 (m), 1026 (m), 682 (m) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.04 (6H, s), 0.88 (12H, m), 1.18–1.70 (30H, m), 1.56–1.70, 3.56–3.70 (6H, m), 4.53 (1H, d, *J* 9.07 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -5.31, 14.13, 18.34, 22.72, 25.83, 25.97 (3C), 29.40–30.51 (8C), 31.59, 31.96, 35.52, 51.03, 51.84, 62.91, 156.80; MS (70 eV) *m/z* (%) 458 (8; M⁺+1), 400 (80), 326 (100; M⁺-OSi(CH₃)₂C(CH₃)₃), 132 (100).

Methyl N-[(1R)-1-(3-hydroxypropyl)pentadecyl]carbamate [(R)-5] : To (*R*)-**4** (0.88 g, 1.92 mmol) was added tetra-*n*-butylammonium fluoride in THF (10 ml, 1 M, 10 mmol). The solution was stirred at room temperature until the reaction was complete by TLC (5 h). Then water (50 ml) was added and the resultant mixture was extracted three times with 50 ml portions of dichloromethane. The combined organic phases was dried over magnesium sulfate, concentrated *in vacuo*, and the residue was purified by flash column chromatography on silica (petroleum ether/ethyl acetate, 1 : 1) to yield (*R*)-**5** (0.62 g, 95%) as a white solid, m.p. 86° (Found : C, 69.75; H, 11.86; N, 4.08. Calcd. : C, 69.92; H, 12.03; N, 3.92%); $[\alpha]_D^{24} = -1.0$ (*c* 0.99, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3319 (s), 2917 (s), 2850 (s), 1693 (s), 1544 (s), 1469 (m), 1353 (m), 1297 (m), 1258 (m), 1040 (m), 1026 (m), 682 (m) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 3.7 Hz), 1.16–1.52 (25H, m), 1.56–1.70 (2H, m), 2.30–2.41 (2H, br), 3.56–3.78 (6H, br), 3.68 (3H, s), 3.72–3.88, 4.63 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.32, 22.88, 26.07, 29.00–29.90 (10C), 32.12, 32.15, 35.78, 51.29, 52.16, 62.73, 157.25; MS (70 eV) *m/z* (%) 344 (6; M⁺+1), 284 (69; M⁺-CO₂CH₃), 146 (100; M⁺-C₁₄H₂₉).

(2R)-(Methyloxycarbonyl)-2-tetradecylpyrrolidine [(R)-6] : To a solution of (*R*)-**5** (0.52 g, 1.5 mmol) and triethylamine (0.33 g, 3.30 mmol) in dichloromethane (8 ml) was added dropwise methanesulfonyl chloride (0.29 g, 2.5 mmol) at 0°. After stirring for 15 min at 0°, ether (10 ml) was added and the mixture was filtered through silica. Concentration of the filtrate under reduced pressure gave the crude mesylate which was dissolved in THF (12 ml) in a flask flushed with argon. At 0° potassium *tert*-butoxide (0.38 g, 3.75 mmol) was added. The mixture was stirred for 30 min at 0° and for 45 min at room temperature. Afterwards, it was poured into water (50 ml) and extracted four times with a total of 150 ml of ether. Drying of the combined organic layers with magnesium sulfate, concentration *in vacuo* and purification by flash column chromatography on silica (petroleum ether/ethyl acetate, 1 : 1) yielded (*R*)-**6** (0.46 g, 95%) as a white waxy solid; ν_{\max} (neat) 2924 (s), 2854 (s), 1707 (s), 1449 (s), 1389 (m), 1339 (m), 1193 (m), 1114 (m), 772 (m), 722 (w); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (3H, t), 1.16–1.36 (25H, m), 1.56–1.70 (2H, br), 1.74–1.95 (3H, m), 3.28–3.48 (2H, br), 3.68 (3H, s), 3.72–3.88 (1H, br); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.14, 22.72, 23.07, 23.91, 26.28, 29.40–30.51 (7C), 31.96, 33.94, 34.46, 46.20, 46.51, 52.06, 57.80, 58.04, 155.6; MS (70 eV) *m/z* (%) 344 (6; M⁺+1), 284 (69; M⁺-CO₂CH₃), 146 (100; M⁺-C₁₄H₂₉), 325 (1; M⁺), 266 (1; M⁺-CO₂CH₃), 128 (100; M⁺-C₁₄H₂₉).

(2R)-N-Methyl-2-tetradecylpyrrolidine [(R)-7] (*bgugaine*): To a solution of (R)-6 (0.34 g, 1 mmol) in THF (20 ml) was added lithium aluminum hydride (0.074 g, 2 mmol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 16 h. The mixture was treated with methanol (1 ml), 2 N NaOH (1 ml), H₂O (1 ml) and dried over potassium carbonate. Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the residue by chromatography on silica (dichloromethane/methanol, 10 : 1) furnished (R)-7 as an oil, $[\alpha]_D^{27} = -45.5$ (c 1.05, MeOH) [lit.³ -45 (c 1.2, MeOH)]; ν_{\max} (neat) 2924 (s), 2853 (s), 2775 (m), 1465 (m), 1043 (w), 721 (w) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz), 1.18–1.36 (25H, m), 1.40–1.47 (1H, m), 1.64–1.73 (1H, m), 1.75–1.80 (1H), 1.90–2.01 (3H, m), 2.14 (1H, m), 2.32 (3H, s), 3.10 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.13, 21.75, 22.70, 26.76, 29.35, 29.63, 29.67, 29.70, 30.02, 30.72, 31.94, 33.62, 40.34, 57.22, 66.56; MS (70 eV) *m/z* (%) 281 (3; M⁺+1), 112 (46), 98 (68), 84 (60), 58 (100).

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References

1. A. Melhau, A. Jossang and B. Bodo, *Nat. Prod. Lett.*, 1993, **3**, 237.
2. A. Melhau, A. Jossang and B. Bodo, *Heterocycles*, 1996, **43**, 755.
3. H. Takahata, K. Ihara, M. Kubota and T. Momose, *Heterocycles*, 1997, **44**, 349.
4. D. Enders and J. Tiebes, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1993, 173.
5. P. G. Mc Dougal, J. G. Rico, Y. -I. Oh and B. D. Condon, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, **51**, 3388.
6. D. Enders in "Asymmetric Synthesis", ed. J. D. Morrison, Academic, Orlando, 1984, Vol. 3, p. 275.